

Supplemental Table S2

Pancreas organ donor information and lesion summary.

Donor	Sex	Age (years)	BMI	HbA _{1c} % (mmol/mol)	Cause of death	Location and number of detected PanIN	Location and number of detected microadenoma	Total number of detected PanIN and microadenoma
1	Female	26	22.2	5.2% (33)	Cerebral hypoxia	Body (2) [†] , tail (1)	None	3
2	Male	37	26.3	5.5% (37)	Traumatic brain injury	Head (2), body (2), tail (4)	None	8
3	Female	40	23.8	5.6% (38)	Cerebrovascular/stroke	Head (1), body (1), tail (1)	None	3
4	Male	50	20.3	5.6% (38)	Brain tumor	Body (2), tail (1)	Tail (2)	5
5	Female	51	19.8	5.3% (34)	Cerebrovascular/stroke	Head (6), body (2)	None	8
6	Female	51	22.8	5.4% (36)	Cerebrovascular/stroke	Head (4), body (3), tail (2)	Head (2)	11
7	Male	53	28.0	6.0% (42)	Subarachnoid hemorrhage	Body (1), tail (2)	Body (1)	4
8	Male	54	23.2	5.4% (36)	Cerebral hypoxia	Body (1)	None	1
9	Female	64	27.1	5.4% (36)	Cerebrovascular/stroke	Head (2), tail (3)	Tail (2)	7
10	Female	65	18.2	6.0% (42)	Cerebrovascular/stroke	Head (1), body (1)	Head (1)	3

[†] Number of lesions indicated in the parentheses.